

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	CTU4H35A
Principle Investigator	Gerhard Groebner
Structure/Description	1-palmitoyl- <i>d</i> ₃₁ -2-oleoyl- <i>d</i> ₃₃ - <i>sn</i> -glycero-phosphoethanolamine
Code	AEL03077
Producer	Anna Leung & Oliver Bogojevic
Mass	23 mg
% Deuteration	97,7% palmitoyl-chain; 98% oleoyl-chain
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other ___ HSQC (¹ H- ¹³ C) NMR spectrum _____

AEL_03077_purified_h400 — AEL_03077_purified — Experiment : 1D 1H

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{33} -sn-glycero-phosphoethanolamine (AEL03077) in CD_3OD (400 MHz).

AEL_03077_purified_h400 — AEL_03077_purified — Experiment : 1D 1H

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{33} -sn-glycero-phosphoethanolamine (AEL03077) in CD_3OD (400 MHz) (expansion).

AEL_03077_purified_ch2d400 — AEL_03077_purified — Experiment : 2

Figure 3. HSQC NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{33} -*sn*-glycero-phosphoethanolamine (AEL03077) in CD_3OD .

Figure 4. ESI-MS(pos) of 1-palmitoyl- d_{31} -2-oleoyl- d_{33} -sn-glycero-phosphoethanolamine (AEL03077): m/z calculated for $C_{39}H_{13}D_{64}NO_8P$ $[M+H]^+$ as 782.9; found: 781.5 (most abundant isotopologue).